

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Sobuddinov Soxibjon

THE INTERACTION BETWEEN THE PRODUCT TO BE GROUND AND
THE GRINDING BLADE IN THE GRINDING CHAMBER

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/IYUN

HONORED
MENTION

YOUR
SEAL